

Navigating the Rebound Effect: Ensuring Efficiency Leads to True Carbon Reductions in High-Performance Computing

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Efficiencies in computation are essential to reducing emissions under the Climate Change Committee (CCC) balanced pathway to net zero.¹ However, there is a concern that upgrades to more efficient equipment intended to reduce the carbon footprint of the DRI will lead to increased demand and utilisation instead of actual carbon savings. Making carbon savings a priority in procurement processes is vital to combat this 'rebound' effect.

If we wish to convert efficiencies into emissions reductions, avoid the rebound effect, and remain aligned with the balanced pathway to net zero, we need a paradigm shift in both the evaluation of computation and procurement requirements.

What is the Rebound effect?

The rebound effect (or Jevons paradox) is about how efficiency measures can lead to increased emissions. In essence, the gains from new technologies that increase the efficiency of resource use can be counteracted by behavioural or other systemic responses that change the way the resources are used (see diagram below).²

In the context of UKRI DRI, we need to ensure measures taken to reduce the carbon footprint and increase efficiency of the DRI are not counteracted by a boost in demand instead of reducing resource use.

The rebound effect reduces expected resource or efficiency savings from new technologies³

¹ [The-Sixth-Carbon-Budget-The-UKs-path-to-Net-Zero.pdf \(theccc.org.uk\)](https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/the-sixth-carbon-budget-the-uks-path-to-net-zero/)

² [Rebound effect \(conservation\) - Wikipedia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rebound_effect_(conservation))

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7016952>

“It is wholly a confusion of ideas to suppose that the economical use of fuel is equivalent to a diminished consumption. The very contrary is the truth. As a rule, new modes of economy will lead to an increase of consumption according to a principle recognised in many parallel instances” - Jevons (1871)

Procurement

Because HPCs⁴ and similar facilities are run at capacity, there are limited actions that can be taken to reduce the carbon footprint during their operation. Efficiency gains, and their impact on UKRI DRI carbon footprint, should be taken into consideration at the procurement stage. UKRI needs to ensure that the procurement framework enables the conversion of efficiency gains into carbon saving.

Upgrading to more efficient equipment should involve considering smaller capacity equipment with greater efficiency that matches the current demand. Then, any additional capacity due to efficiency gains will be converted into carbon savings, maximising the reduction in carbon emissions.

The moment a large computer is procured, decisions about how to deliver and achieve a scientific throughput are constrained by technical targets. UKRI procurement needs to include metrics that relate to strategic objectives of societal benefit and the net-zero target, not simply technical targets.

Furthermore, the implementation of a review process at the procurement stage and involving hardware experts in the procurement process can ensure well intentioned measures do not trigger the rebound effect.

DRI use

There is tension between the limitations necessary to achieve net zero without putting limitations on research and innovation. However, carbon should be considered a limited resource in the same way as financial resources, and it is pragmatic to consider carbon under a similar principle of constraint.

The limitations necessary for the implementation of Net Zero DRI and avoiding the rebound effect provide an opportunity for UKRI to set an example in sustainable research. We must be innovative with the technology we use and the way we use it to minimise demand whilst maximising efficiency. Although procurement processes are not in the hands of users of HPC equipment, it is the responsibility of everyone to consider the carbon impact of their work and the demand it puts on the environment.

⁴ High Performance Computers

Conclusion

Increased efficiency from technological advances should be framed as an opportunity for reductions in emissions and not just increased capacity.

A paradigm shift in the way we think about increased efficiency is necessary in both the way we procure and manage DRI equipment and our expectations on DRI capacity as a non-infinite, valuable asset.

Further information

York, Richard (2006). "Ecological paradoxes: William Stanley Jevons and the paperless office". In: *Human Ecology Review*, pp. 143–147 (cit. on p. 48).

<https://www.humanecologyreview.org/pastissues/her132/york.pdf>

Trincado, Estrella, Antonio Sanchez-Bayon, and Jose Maria Vindel (July 2021). "The European Union Green Deal: Clean Energy Wellbeing Opportunities and the Risk of the Jevons Paradox". English. In: *ENERGIES* 14.14. DOI: [10.3390/en14144148](https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144148) (cit. on p. 48).

Juckes, M., Pascoe, C., Woodward, L., Vanderbauwhede, W., & Weiland, M. (2022). Interim Report: Complexity, Challenges and Opportunities for Carbon Neutral Digital Research.

Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7016952>

Supporting recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)⁵.

A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 7: Avoid the rebound effect at the procurement stage. Ensure the procurement framework enables the conversion of efficiency gains into carbon savings rather than simply resulting in higher usage.

Recommendation 161: UKRI must ensure that steps taken to reduce environmental impact do not end up having the opposite effect through feedbacks such as the rebound, or Jevons, effect.

Recommendation 31: Establish and follow best practice in sustainable use of DRI by researchers.

⁵ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>